

QISHLOQ XO‘JALIGI EKINLARINING SUG‘ORISH ME‘YORLARI VA ULARNING EKINLARNI RIVOJLANISHIGA TA‘SIRI ORQALI ANIQLASH

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada hozirgi kundagi suv taqchili va buning sabablari hamda qishloq xo‘jaligi ekinlarining sug‘orish me‘yorlari va ularning g‘o‘za tuplarini rivojlanishiga ta‘siri to‘g‘risidagi takliflar va tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Аннотация: на этом статье приведена в настоящие время водонедостаточности и их фактори а также норма полива сельско хозяйственного культуры и рекомендаця и предложение их влияние о развитие каждого стеблей хлопчатника.

Abstract: this article presents current water shortages and their factors, as well as the rate of irrigation of agricultural crops and recommendations and proposals for their influence on the development of each cotton stem.

Kalit so‘zlar: suv, resurs, me‘yor, samara, taqchil, qishloq xo‘jaligi, g‘o‘za, tup, egat.

Ключевой слово: вода, ресурс, норма, эффект, недостатка. Сельского хозяйство, хлопка, стеблей, окучка.

Keyword: water: resource, rate, effect, deficiency. Agriculture, cotton, stalks, spud.

Dunyoning juda ko‘p mintaqalarida, jumladan mamlakatimizda suv resurslariga bo‘lgan talab oshib borishi bilan birga, suvning taqchilligi ham yildan-yilga kuchayib bormoqda. Suvning taqchilligi xususan daryolarning quyi qismlarida, suv manbailaridan uzoqda joylashgan iste‘molchilarga kuchli sezilmoqda. Shu boisdan respublikamizda suv resurslaridan samarali va tejamli foydalanish asosida sug‘oriladigan ekin maydonlaridan olinadigan hosilning miqdorini oshirish, qishloq xo‘jalik maxsulotlarining ishlab chiqarishni kengaytirish, sifatini yaxshilash, shuningdek ichki bozorni qishloq xo‘jalik maxsulotlari bilan to‘ldirish orqali mamlakat aholisining yashash sharoitini yanada yaxshilash borasida samarali ishlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Mamlakatimizda suvdan maqsadli va samarali foydalanish bo‘yicha keyingi yillarda keng ko‘lamda ishlar olib borilmoqda.

O‘zbekistonning umumiy yer maydoni 44892,4 ming gektarni tashkil etadi. Ushbu yerlar foydalanish maqsadi va tartibiga ko‘ra 8 ta toifaga bo‘linadi:

jumladan, qishloq xo'jaligiga mo'ljallangan yerlar, aholi punktlarining yerlari, transport, aloqa, mudofaa va boshqa maqsadlarga mo'ljallangan yerlar, tabiatni muhofaza qilish, sog'lashtirish va rekreatsiya maqsadlariga mo'ljallangan yerlar, tarixiy-madaniy ahamiyatga molik yerlar, o'rmon fondi yerlari, suv fondi yerlari, zahira yerlar.

Respublikamizning qishloq xo'jaligiga mo'ljallangan yerlarining umumiy maydoni 20236,3 ming gektarni tashkil etib, umumiy boyligimiz bo'lgan qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish va mamlakat oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning asosiy vositasi hisoblanadi. Shundan haydaladigan yerlar 3988,5ming gektarni, ko'p yillik daraxtzorlar 383,1 ming gektarni, bo'z yerlar 76 ming gektarni, pichanzor va yaylovlar 11028,3 ming gektarni, boshqa yerlar 4760,4 ming gektarni tashkil qiladi.

Qishloq xo'jaligida o'rtacha yillik suv sarfi 45696 mln m³ ni yoki iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida iste'mol qilinayotgan suv resurslarining 90% ni tashkil etib, yuqoriligicha qolmoqda. Yer va suv resurslari tobora taqchil bo'lib borayotgan sharoitda qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarini joylashtirishda ekinlarning iqtisodiy samaradorligi va bozor kon'yunkturasi inobatga olinmasdan hamda intensiv qishloq xo'jaligi texnikalari va texnologiyalari to'liq joriy etilmaganligi sababli qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish hajmi pastligicha qolmoqda. Jumladan, rivojlangan davlatlarda 1 m³ suv bilan 4-6 AQSh dollarlik mahsulot yetishtirilayotgan bo'lsa, bu ko'rsatgich respublikamizda 0,15 AQSh dollarini tashkil etmoqda.

Yuqoridagilarni inobatga olgan holda qishloq xo'jaligi ekinlarini sug'orishda, suvning me'yori va uning o'simlikning rivojlanishiga ta'siri orqali aniqlash, suvning tejamkorligiga o'zining ijobiy ta'sirini ko'rsatadi. Shu sababli biz sug'orish me'yorlarini aniqlash bo'yicha fikr va muloxazalarimiz bayon qilmoqchimiz.

Sug'orish me'yori- bu g'o'zaning vegetatsiya davrida 1 gektar sug'oriladigan maydonga beriladigan suvning miqdori. Umumiy sug'orish me'yori bir necha alohida berish me'yorlari orqali aniqlanadi. Bir marotaba sug'orishda ekinning ildiz tizimlari joylashgan tuproq qatlamining o'zida ushlab qoldigan miqdordagi suv berish lozim bo'ladi. Sug'orish rejimi va me'yori sug'orish usuli bilan uzviy bog'liq bo'ladi. Egat qatorlari orqali sug'orishda egatning uzunligi bo'ylab bir tekisda namlanishga erishish uchun suv berish me'yori 1 gektarga 600 m³ dan kam bo'lmasligi kerak. G'o'zaning rivojlanish davri bo'yicha sug'orishlar soni quyidagicha bo'lishi mumkin: mug'jalashgacha 1yoki 2 marta, gullash davrida 2 yoki 3 marta, ko'sakning yetilib pishish davrida 2 martagacha bo'ladi.

G'o'za rivojlanishining birinchi yarmidagi sug'orish rejimi, uning rivojlanishini

keyingi davrlariga va hosildorligiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatadi. G'ozaning gullash-hosil tugish davrida namlikning umumiy sarfi vegetatsiya davridagi suvning umumiy sarfidan 55-65% ni tashkil qiladi. Shu sababli ushbu davrda sug'orish g'ozaga ko'saklarini rivojlanishiga, saqlab qolishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Dehqon-fermerlar yillar davomida ortirgan o'zlarini malakalari hisobidan kelib chiqqan holda sug'orish muddatlarini quyidagi usullar orqali belgilaydilar: 1- tuproqning namligiga qarab ya'ni sug'oriladigan maydonning diagonali bo'yicha uchta nuqtada aniqlanadi: g'ozaning shonalashgacha bo'lgan davrda tuproqning namligiga qarab ildizning rivojlanish qatlami hisobga olinadi, bu qatlam 50 sm.gacha, shonalash davridan gullash davrining boshlanishigacha 70 sm.gacha, gullashdan hosilga kirib pishgungacha davrda 100 sm.gacha bo'lishi kerak. 2-asosiy tup (poya)ning o'sib rivojlanishiga qarab: g'ozaning shonalash davrida o'rtacha bir sutkalik o'sishi 0,3-0,5 sm, asosiy tup(poya)ning yerdan uchigacha balandligi 14-18 sm. bo'lishi kerak. G'ozaning gullab hosilga o'tirish davrida o'rtacha bir sutkalik o'sishi 0,8-1,5 sm. gacha, g'ozapoyasining umumiy 40-50 sm.gacha bo'ladi. g'ozaga ko'saklarining pishish davrida asosiy tupning o'sishi 0,8-1,3 sm.gacha, umumiy balandligi esa 80-90 sm.gacha boradi. 3-barglarining rangini o'zgarishiga qarab ya'ni bargi och yashil rangdan to'q yashilga o'zgaradi. G'ozaga maydoning taxminan 20% i och yashildan to'q yashil rangga o'zgarganda sug'orishni amalga oshirish kerak. 4- bargning o'zagini mustahkamligini o'zgarishiga qarab: Asosiy tupning yuqori uchidan 3- nchi yoki 4-inchi bargda havoning issiq vaqtida uning o'zgini aniqlash lozim. Agarda g'ozaning tupida namlik yetarli bo'lmasa, uning bargini egganda. bargning markaziy o'zagidan tovush chiqmasdan sinadi. Taxminan ekin dalasidagi 20% o'simlikning barglarida shunday holat kuzatilganda g'ozaning sug'orishni amalga oshirish kerak bo'ladi.

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